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ViSS non-sensitive ICT Platform/D6.1

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PU = Public

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1. List of abbreviations

API: Application Programming Interface

DoA: Description of the Action

ICT: Information and communication Technology

LCA: Life Cycle Analysis

LCC: Life Costs Cycle

SLCA: Social Life Cycle Analysis.

SRL: Social Readiness Assessment Framework

SSbD: Safe and Sustainable by Design

URL: Uniform Resource Locators

WP: Work Package

2. Objectives and scope

This Deliverable D6.1 (*ViSS non-sensitive ICT Platform*) complements Deliverable D6.2 (*ViSS sensitive ICT Platform*), both belonging to Task 6.1 (Development and implementation of the ViSS ICT Platform) of Work Package 6 (WP6) *ViSS Safe and Sustainable by design assurance and creation of enabling conditions*, which aims at developing and implementing the ViSS ICT Platform.

Specifically, D.6.1 aims to present the development of the Evaluation and Decision Tool and the Public Tool, while D6.2 focuses on the development of the Traceability Tool.

These tasks have been developed in parallel with T6.2, T6.3 and T6.4 which aim to develop the SSbD and Social Readiness Assessment Framework (SRL).

Once the safety, economic, environmental and social criteria and factors have been defined, and the ViSS evaluation framework, consisting of the SSbD matrix, has been linked to the development of the SRL (the protocols/methodologies and means of evaluation, monitoring and data collection), which will feed the Evaluation and Decision Tool, a computer analysis and development will have to be carried out to integrate the evaluation matrix and the scoring system developed in 6.2, with the data collected and the instruments implemented within the following Tasks 6.3 & 6.4 by IDE (IDENER) & KVC (KVELOCE).

As for the Public Tool, a first framework will be developed, with the data to be provided by KVC, to communicate the impact of the project while raising awareness by providing consumers with reliable information.

The development of the ViSS ICT platform will be carried out by integrating the results of 4 tasks (see Figure 1). In order to meet these requirements, it has been necessary to interpret the work done by KVC and IDE in relation to the Safe and Sustainable by Design approach, which together with the data to be provided in due course by VTT with the results of the LCA, will be used to develop the ViSS ICT platform.

Figure 1. Methodology for the Development of ViSS ICT Platform.

Following the description of the work in WP6 and the approach already defined for the Traceability Tool (see D6.2) and the SSbD (see D6.3), the development of this tool has been divided into five phases:

Phase 1: the baseline report D6.1 (ViSS non-sensitive ICT Platform (M6)) with a description of the methodological approach used, including the objective and scope of the assessment and the data collection strategy.

Phase 2: Interim report D6.4 (First integration and assessment of data in ICT Platform (M12)): report on the advancement on the ViSS Tools allocated in the ICT platform and integration of the ViSS data into the respective tools

Phase 3: Interim report D6.5 (Second integration and assessment of data in ICT Platform (M12-18)): report on the advancement on the ViSS tools allocated in the ICT platform and integration of the ViSS data into the respective tools

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Phase 4: Interim report D6.8 (Third integration and assessment of data in ICT Platform, (M18-33)): Report on the advancement on the ViSS Tools allocated in the ICT platform and integration of the ViSS data into the respective tools

Phase 5: Final report D6.13 (Final integration and assessment of data in ICT Platform (M47): final integration of ViSS data: data from WP1-WP5 developments into the Traceability tool, data from WP6 (SSbD, SRL) into the Evaluation & Decision tool and their assessment, and the data for the general public in the Public Tool.

Therefore, the objective of this deliverable (D6.1) is to prepare the ground by providing a brief overview of the methodology for the development of the Decision and Public tools, proposing the methodological approach to evaluate and incorporate the protocols/methodologies and means of evaluation, monitoring and data collection to feed these tools.

In addition, as the results of the project impacts are generated, this information will be provided through the Public Tool, to provide consumers with reliable information and at the same time raise awareness in the field of the SSbD.

3. Introduction

As part of the ViSS initiative, in WP6, an ICT platform has been developed for capturing, storing, processing, and securely communicating information throughout the ViSS solution approach. The tool ensures transparency in materials, ingredients and aids used in all the lifecycle processes to be able to prove that it is possible to make packaging from residues from the candy and poultry industries.

It is an intuitive and easy-to-use tool, configured to sign up and generate unique identifiers from waste streams, updating their properties with the different processes they go through until they are transformed into final products such as packaging.

The present deliverable covers the methodology proposed for the Evaluation and Decision Tool and Public Tool development.

Deliverable 6.1, which was due on May 31, 2024, was submitted on July 7, 2024, due to a delay. In the updated version (v2.0, submitted on September 2025), a justification for this delay has been provided in line with European Commission (EC) recommendations. The delay was primarily caused by the strong interdependence between the present deliverable and D6.3 (SSbD and Social Readiness evaluation framework). Both deliverables had the same submission date, however, D6.1 required the methodological outputs and evaluation criteria defined in D6.3 in order to correctly implement the Evaluation and Decision Tool within the ICT platform.

Specifically, this non sensitive part of the platform needed as inputs a robust and well-defined evaluation matrix and scoring system. The development of the Evaluation and Decision Tool could only proceed once the consensus on SSbD and SRL dimensions, categories and indicators was finalised in D6.3.

4. Evaluation and Decision Tool

The Evaluation and Decision Tool will allow technical partners to make decisions based on the different aspects regarded in the SSbD evaluation matrix. It is a private tool used by technical partners, not consumers, to guide them across their productions to achieve the project objectives in terms of safety and sustainability of materials and products.

Each product will have its own scoring value, which will be the metric to compare the selected solution to other production processes and even to other products on the market.

Figure 2: ViSS SSbD approach and strategy to create enabling conditions, involving all actors.

To ensure that all materials involved in ViSS are traceable and that ViSS sustainability claims are reliable and fair, while supporting SSbD and social readiness assessment, ViSS will develop an ICT-platform (non-AI based), based on blockchain technology, by adapting the ICT similar platform developed by CETEC in the EU project Agro2Circular^{1,2}. This platform will integrate 3 tools:

1. **Traceability Tool** will allow information to be obtained and communicated safely and effectively throughout the ViSS value chain.
2. **Evaluation and Decision Tool** that will integrate the developed SSbD and Social readiness common evaluation matrix to both help the evaluation of the social readiness and the decision-making through the technical developments based on safe and sustainable criteria. At commercialisation stage, it will help industrial end-users to respond to their requirements based on safety and sustainability performance linked to ViSS materials & products functionalities.

¹ Navarro, S.; Monzón, F.; Arribas, A.; Benítez, S.; López, P. (2023) Proyecto agro2circular: una solución sistémica para los residuos plásticos alimentarios. *Actas del X Simposio Iberoamericano de Ingeniería de Residuos: Hacia la circularidad y el residuo cero*. ISBN 978-84-09-53123-3.

² Ortiz, J.; Viso, A. (2023) Herramienta software de trazabilidad de residuos. *Actas del X Simposio Iberoamericano de Ingeniería de Residuos: Hacia la circularidad y el residuo cero*. ISBN 978-84-09-53123-3

3. **Public Tool** geared towards providing consumers with reliable information.

4.1 Dimensions and Levels

Gathered from D6.3, there have been distinguished a set of levels to arrange the different studied criteria. Starting from the most general layer, five areas of decision are taken into consideration, these topics are the ones presented as the different cores that comply the SSbD³ (Figure 3).

Figure 3: SSBD overview

As it can be seen, the two big sections to cover are the safety and sustainability dimensions, which disaggregated are composed by the different levels seen in Figure 2

Figure 4: Dimensions, from D6.3. Adapted from EU Commission, 2022

These designs are replicated into a product as follows in Table 1.

Design	Product
Safety	SbD
Environmentally sustainable	LCA
Economically sustainable	LCC
Socially sustainable	sLCA

³ Caldeira, C., Farcas, L., Moretti, C., Mancini, L., Rasmussen, K., Rauscher, H., Riego Sintes, J., Sala, S. (2022a). Safe and Sustainable by design chemicals and materials – Review of safety and sustainability dimensions, aspects, methods, indicators, and tools (EUR 30991). Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2760/879069>

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Table 1: Relation between designs and products. Caldeira et al. 22

Starting from this point, it has been able to differentiate different categories to be studied in each one of the levels, grouped by different aspects and finally being able to identify the indicators, which are the most accurate ways of scoring the system.

Given this information, Table 2 has been disposed as a general view of the different terms to take into consideration.

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DIMENSION	Safety			ESbD				CSbD				SoSbD				
CATEGORY	Hazard properties	Production	Aplication	Climate change	Toxicity	Pollution	Resources	Product cost	Life cycle cost and externality cost	Market-related criteria	Profitability analysis	Workers	Chain valour Actor	Society	Local	Consumers
ASPECT	Human health hazards	Acute human health hazards	Human health	Climate change	Human toxicity cancer	Ozone depletion	Water use	Purchase cost	Externality cost	Willingness to pay	Normalised added value [-]	Forced labour	Fair competition	Public commitment to sustainability issues	Access to material resources	Health and safety
	Environmental Hazards	Chronic human health hazards	Environmental toxicity		Human toxicity, non cancer	Particulate matter	Land use	Production cost (Total)	Cost of waste treatment	Product performance	Profitability	Fair salary	Promoting social responsibility	Contributions to economic development	Access to immaterial resources	Feedback mechanism
	Physical properties	Physical properties			Ecotoxicity	Ionizing radiation	Resource use, fossil	Minimum selling price	Environmental taxes		Net present value	Working hours	Supplier relationships	Technology development	Delocalization and migration	Transparency
		Release Behaviour				Photochemical ozone formation	Resource use, minerals and metals		Environmental subsidies		Added value	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Wealth distribution	Corruption (value chain actors)	Cultural heritage	End-of-life responsibility
		Process related hazards risk				Acidification	Cumulative energy demand		Externality cost (€)		Payback period	Health and safety		Poverty alleviation	Safe and healthy living conditions	Affordability
						Eutrophication, terrestrial					Financial profit	Social benefits, legal issues, social security			Community engagement	
						Eutrophication, freshwater						Workers' rights / Freedom of association and collective bargaining			Local employment	
						Eutrophication, marine						Sexual harassment			Secure living conditions	

Table 2: Levels of aggregation hierarchy: dimensions, categories and aspects. Based in SSbD-JRC128591 ⁴

4.2 Selected categories and aspects of each dimension and level.

According to the results and methodology presented in D6.3, the dimensions of Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) have been analyzed and evaluated preliminarily. To proceed with creating the ViSS Evaluation and Decision Tool, several steps are being taken. The first step involved selecting the categories and sort of aspects that ViSS consortium experts deemed impactful and relevant.

Next critical action for designing this tool is evaluating and integrating data generated in Tasks 6.2, 6.3, and 6.4. Each step described in the sections will be assigned a score, and aggregating these scores will yield an overall SCORE. All metrics will be given a score, from indicators to categories.

As introduced according to the results presented in D6.3, the assessment procedure is based on a hierarchical principle in which a first step consists of assessing aspects that are mandatory and with exclusion criteria based on an “SSbD SCORE system”⁴.

This score has four components, one reflecting the Safety assessment, one showing the result of the environmental sustainability assessment, one reflecting the social sustainability assessment and one on the economic sustainability (showing the results of the cost analysis assessment).

The final result of the assessment can be expressed as an SSbD rating class (passed, failed) or with a numerical score derived from the combination of the individual scores on each aspect (e.g. subject to weighting). These options will be explored when more data becomes available and will be presented in the interim reports, where a set of requirements to be taken into account when proposing an overall assessment procedure will be further defended.

The application of the presented criteria will lead to multiple assessments that can be combined using MCDA (Multiple-criteria decision analysis) to support decision making in SSbD⁵. Multi-attribute aggregation methods can be used both to aggregate multiple aspects under one dimension at different levels of an aggregation hierarchy and to aggregate the high-level Dimensions (safety, environmental, social and economic sustainability).

⁴ Caldeira C., Farcal R., Garmendia Aguirre, I., Mancini, L., Tosches, D., Amelio, A., Rasmussen, K., Rauscher, H., Riego Sintes J., Sala S. Safe and Sustainable by Design chemicals and materials - Framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for chemicals and materials. EUR 31100 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-53264-4, doi:10.2760/487955, JRC128591 Pages (59-66)

⁵ Luis C. Dias, Carla Caldeira, Serenella Sala, Multiple criteria decision analysis to support the design of safe and sustainable chemicals and materials, Science of The Total Environment, Volume 916, 2024, 169599, ISSN 0048-9697, doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.169599.

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Figure 5: Hierarchy of assessment attributes. JRC JRC128591 ⁴

The result is an aggregation of rating levels given as input must be obtained to provide an output as a rating level. As there are several possibilities for MCDA analysis, as more data becomes available, new aggregation systems will be reconsidered.

Based on the results presented in D6.3 (SSbD and Social Readiness Level evaluation framework (SRL))^{6,7}, a first aggregation proposal has been made, based on the results, based on the scoring criteria set out in that task.

- In terms of costs the evaluation of the results proposes 4 categories by importance: product cost, life cycle cost and cost of externalities, market related criteria and cost-effectiveness analysis.
- In the social dimension, the categories selected were workers, value chain actors, society, local community and consumers.

Table 3 shows the results of the acquired data from the workshop carried out by KVC during the first General Assembly Meeting.

The assessment scores of the Social and Economic Categories and Aspects follow the following color scheme:

- Red: Principles and Aspects that scored 3.5 or less than 3.5 in average.
- Orange: Principles and Aspects that scored more than 3.5 but less than 4.5.
- Green: Principles and Aspects that scored 4.5 or more.

⁶ UNEP. (2020). Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020. Benoît Norris, C., Traverso, M., Neugebauer, S., Ekener, E., Schaubroeck, T., Russo Garrido, S., Berger, M., Valdivia, S., Lehmann, A., Finkbeiner, M., Arcese, G. (eds.). United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). <https://wedocs.unep.org/handle/20.500.11822/34554>

⁷ UNEP. (2021). Methodological Sheets for Subcategories in Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) M. Traverso, S. Valdivia, A. Luthin, L. Roche, G. Arcese, S. Neugebauer, L. Petti, M. D'Eusano, B. M. Tragnone, R. Mankaa, J. Hanafi, C. Benoit-Norris, A. Zamagni (eds.)

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CSbD				SoSbD				
Product cost	Life cycle cost and externality cost	Market-related criteria	Profitability analysis	Workers	Value chain Actor	Society	Local	Consumers
Purchase price	Externality cost	Willingness to pay	Normalized added value (%)	Forced labour	Fair competition	Public commitment to sustainability issues	Access to material resources	Quality and safety
Production cost margin	Cost of waste treatment	Product performance	Profitability	Fair salary	Promoting social responsibility	Contributions to economic development	Access to financial resources	Feedback mechanism
Minimum selling price	Environmental taxes	Subsidies requirements	Net present value	Working hours	Supplier relationships	Technology development	Delocalization and migration	Transparency
	Environmental subsidies	Value-chain collaboration	Added value	Equal opportunities / Discrimination	Wealth distribution	Corruption (value chain actors)	Cultural heritage	Environmental responsibility
	Externality cost (€)		Payback period	Health and safety		Poverty alleviation	Safe and healthy living conditions	Affordability
			Financial profit	Social benefits, legal issues, social security			Community engagement	
				Workers' rights / Freedom of association and collective bargaining			Local employment	
				Sexual harassment			Secure living conditions	

Table 3: Workshop results

4.3. Case study

We present a case study based on the social dimension of the variables to be contained in the decision tool based on the preliminary results of Task 6.3. These options will be further discussed and tested in intermediate reports in order to select the most appropriate solution for the SSbD Evaluation and Decision Tool.

Based on these hypotheses and in relation to the impact and relevance of the categories, aspects and indicators analysed in D6.3, a first scoring system, selection of categories, aspects as well as selected indicators has been proposed and is presented in Table 4.

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DIMENSION	CATEGORY	ASPECT	INDICATOR
SOCIAL	Workers	Forced labour	Employment terms
			Forced Labour
		Fair salary	Living wage per month
			Minimum wage, per month
			Organisation average wage, per month
		Working hours	Flexibility
			Full-time staff
		Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Gender equality
			Equal opportunities policies
		Health and safety	Occupational safety measures
	Lost time injury frequency rate		
	Social benefits, legal issues, social security	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	
	Workers' rights / Freedom of association and collective bargaining	Trade unions density	
		Collective Bargaining Agreement	
	Sexual harassment	Sexual harassment incidents reported	
	Value chain actors	Fair competition	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour
		Promoting social responsibility	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility
			Suppliers audit
		Supplier relationships	Suppliers' communication relationship
		Wealth distribution	Fair price definition
	Respect intellectual property rights	Number of property rights infringements	
	Society	Public commitment to sustainability issues	Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues
		Contributions to economic development	Total taxation per capita
		Technology development	Technology transfer
			Investments in technology development/ transfer
		Corruption (value chain actors)	Corruption
		Poverty alleviation	Poverty alleviation programme
	Local community	Access to material resources	Environmental management system
		Access to immaterial resources	Community education initiatives
		Delocalization and migration	Immigrant workforce rate
			Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community
		Cultural heritage	Funding dedicated to support and promote cultural heritage
		Safe and healthy living conditions	Promotion of community health
		Community engagement	Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation
			Number of meetings with community stakeholders
		Local employment	Workforce hired locally
			Spending on locally based suppliers
	Secure living conditions	Security complaints by the community	
	Consumers	Health and safety	Labelling
			Consumer complaints
			Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System
		Feedback mechanism	Presence of consumers feedback mechanism
		Transparency	Organisation communication transparency
		End-of-life responsibility	Internal management systems
	Affordability	Potential price in comparison to market equivalent	

Table 4: Indicators to measure of the given categories.

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The criteria to be integrated within the tool can be defined, to facilitate the integration of data to the users of the tool, thus facilitating the analysis and evaluation of the materials/packaging that can be proposed, to see, on the basis of the SSbD, whether it exceeds the criteria defined for safety, environmental, social and economic sustainability described in the previous section. The idea of a scoring system is to allow the classification of those that are SSbD and those that are not.

The scoring system has been described by KVC for accepting or rejecting solutions. It is the way technical partners will evaluate the degree of improvement with the position reference. The scoring values are presented in Table 5.

Position to reference [market bench march, conventional product]	Score	Colour code	Level
No improvement*	0	Red	Fail the criteria
Improvement -5%	1	Orange	
Improvement +5% to 20%	2	Yellow	Pass the criteria
Improvement +20% to 40%	3	Light Green	
Improvement >40%	4	Blue	

Table 5: Scoring system values (the positions to reference might vary following the Indicator), based on Caldeira et al 2022⁸.

It has been proposed to evaluate the indicators 0-4, and taking into account some considerations such as: if one aspect fails the evaluation, the category is automatically rejected until the different indicators on the solution pass the evaluation and the aspect gets passed.

For helping technical partners to evaluate each indicator, there will be given a description and a benchmark of them.

Figure 3 shows an example on the LCA, provided by KVC.

⁸ European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Caldeira, C., Farcas, L., Garmendia Aguirre, I. et al., *Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials – Framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for chemicals and materials*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/487955>

LCA Assessment level (max score)	Aspect	Score	Level
Toxicity ES1 (max 12)	Human Toxicity, cancer	3	✗
	Human Toxicity non cancer	2	
	Ecotoxicity	1	
Climate Change ES2 (max 4)	Climate Change	3	✓
Pollution ES3 (max 32)	Ozone depletion	4	✗
	Particulate matter/Respiratory inorganics	2	
	Ionising radiation, human health	2	
	Photochemical ozone formation	1	
	Acidification	0	
	Eutrophication, terrestrial	-4	
	Eutrophication, aquatic freshwater	3	
Eutrophication, aquatic marine	2		
Resources ES4 (max 16)	Land Use	4	✓
	Water use	2	
	Resource use, minerals and metals	2	
	Resource use, energy carriers	2	

Figure 6: Example of environmental evaluation table, Caldeira et al. 22

In this example the Categories [in this example it is called Assessment level] POLLUTION and TOXICITY would be, as a whole, rejected. The other 2 accepted. The Aspects (and related Indicators) Ecotoxicity, Photochemical ozone formation and Acidification should be improved to pass the Environmental dimension.

Following this theoretical case study, text below shows the ICT Platform for the Evaluation and Decision Tool, described per figure on the social evaluation:

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Figure 7 shows the dashboard when no evaluation has been done.

Figure 7: Evaluation and Decision Tool. Empty dashboard

Figure 8 shows the different selected indicators on the social dimension. These are the ones proposed by KVC on the D6.3 matrix.

Figure 8: Evaluation and Decision Tool. Social indicators

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On the evaluation page, the technical user will be able to select the different dimensions and the indicators to cover, shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Evaluation and Decision Tool. Select indicators

Next, the tool allows the user to select multiple indicators to evaluate at the same time. Each indicator has associated a description for making the usage easier to the evaluator. Once the benchmarks and starting points are set, they will be included in the description to be able to guide the user. This functionality is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Evaluation and Evaluation Tool. Evaluate indicators

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Finally, Figures 11 and 12 show the information of the evaluation to the user in graphs and tables. These displays are updated in real-time each time a new evaluation is submitted.

Figure 11: Evaluation and Decision Tool. Dashboard updated

Figure 12: Evaluation and Decision Tool. Multi-evaluation - Aspect evaluation

This section covers a proposed example by CETEC. Technical users will take part in the evaluation display for making improvements.

4.4. Technological requirements

These requirements come in parallel with the above-described work of analyzing the different criteria to cover. They aim to show how the information is going to be connected and how the technical partners will be able to interact with it.

The preliminary design is a set of URLs that will be accessible from the <https://viss.erantum.com/> home page. On the frontend side, it will show forms for technical partner's evaluation, on building the scoring system and the selected representation methods identified in the above section. On the other hand, on the backend side, the main functionality will be the Laravel's based API that will connect the Evaluation and Decision Tool to the Traceability Tool, to show statistics and link the scoring system with the manufactured products.

5. Public Tool

The main objective of the Public Tool is to communicate to all the society and citizens the ViSS project impacts and raise awareness on sustainability.

This tool is at an early stage as it is needed to define which information is key to communicate. This work is also very related to the *WP7 Communication, dissemination & exploitation and capacity building*, as it involves efficient and tailored measures & actions such as: A CDE comprehensive strategy and its tools; awareness, networking & clustering and capacity building actions, cooperation with initiatives including the KCB and the share of methodologies with other projects funded under this topic and others with an SSbD approach (enabling common approaches); public engagement strategy to support communication & dissemination and the SRL assessment while enhancing acceptability and increasing awareness. This strategy relies on the Quadruple Helix of Stakeholders: Decision makers; private organisations & business, academia & research entities; citizens & civil society organisations; exploitation actions: business planning, IPR management, innovation monitoring and market analysis ensuring optimal post-project exploitation.

The preliminary decision is that this Tool is shown in the ViSS official website or the ICT Tool home page as accountability for communication.

As soon as these impacts become materialized, they will be shown as proposed, for the moment due to the stage of the technical work, there is not anything to communicate.

6. Conclusions

This preliminary report presents the methodology and approach for the design and development of the Decision and Public tool. The objective and scope have been defined, including the selection of parameters to assess as well as the scoring system to facilitate its evaluation.

When using a decision tool for the first time it is important to recognise that it is not a perfect tool. The accuracy and applicability of the output will depend on the reliability of the data. The reality of each category, sub-category and indicator selected for analysis and decision must be defined by data and measurements that can be verifiable.

The data collection tool has been prepared and tested for the analysis of at least the economic and social levels according to the results of Task 6.3. It will be shared with the partners constituting the value chain as soon as data from the first results of each task are available.

Relevant data will be collected gradually and added systematically considering the progress of the project in its different phases, where an updated version will be presented in each interim report, which will collect and analyse inventory data on technologies and processes.

7. References

- [1] Navarro, S.; Monzón, F.; Arribas, A.; Benítez, S.; López, P. (2023) Proyecto Agro2circular: una solución sistémica para los residuos plásticos alimentarios. Actas del X Simposio Iberoamericano de Ingeniería de Residuos: Hacia la circularidad y el residuo cero. ISBN 978-84-09-53123-3.
- [2] Ortiz, J.; Viso, A. (2023) Herramienta software de trazabilidad de residuos. Actas del X Simposio Iberoamericano de Ingeniería de Residuos: Hacia la circularidad y el residuo cero. ISBN 978-84-09-53123-3
- [3] Caldeira, C., Farcas, L., Moretti, C., Mancini, L., Rasmussen, K., Rauscher, H., Riego Sintés, J., Sala, S. (2022a). Safe and Sustainable by design chemicals and materials – Review of safety and sustainability dimensions, aspects, methods, indicators, and tools (EUR 30991). Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2760/879069>
- [4] Caldeira C., Farcas R., Garmendia Aguirre, I., Mancini, L., Tosches, D., Amelio, A., Rasmussen, K., Rauscher, H., Riego Sintés J., Sala S. Safe and Sustainable by Design chemicals and materials - Framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for chemicals and materials. EUR 31100 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-53264-4, doi:10.2760/487955, JRC128591 Pages (59-66)
- [5] Luis C. Dias, Carla Caldeira, Serenella Sala, Multiple criteria decision analysis to support the design of safe and sustainable chemicals and materials, Science of The Total Environment, Volume 916, 2024, 169599, ISSN 0048-9697, doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.169599.
- [6] UNEP. (2020). Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020. Benoît Norris, C., Traverso, M., Neugebauer, S., Ekener, E., Schaubroeck, T., Russo Garrido, S., Berger, M., Valdivia, S., Lehmann, A., Finkbeiner, M., Arcese, G. (eds.). United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). <https://wedocs.unep.org/handle/20.500.11822/34554>
- [7] UNEP. (2021). Methodological Sheets for Subcategories in Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) M. Traverso, S. Valdivia, A. Luthin, L. Roche, G. Arcese, S. Neugebauer, L. Petti, M. D'Eusanio, B. M. Tragnone, R. Mankaa, J. Hanafi, C. Benoit-Norris, A. Zamagni (eds.)
- [8] European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Caldeira, C., Farcas, L., Garmendia Aguirre, I. et al., Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials – Framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for chemicals and materials, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/487955>